

Supplementary Information

Viridicatin from the Antarctic fungus *Penicillium* sp. protects human microglia and patient-derived peripheral immune cells against oxidative stress

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A Single crystal X-ray structure analysis of viridicatin

1. General details of X-ray structure analysis

The crystal structure was determined by single crystal structure analysis. A suitable single crystal was selected using a Leica M205C light microscope and separated with oil. X-ray crystal structure analysis was performed on a Stadivari diffractometer (Stoe) with monochromated Mo- $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). The data correction was performed using the program X-Area.¹ The structure was solved by direct methods and refined against F^2 on all data by full-matrix least-squares using the SHELX suite of programs.^{2,3} All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically; the hydrogen atoms were placed on calculated positions. **Table S1** was created using FinalCif.⁴ The crystal structure was visualized with Mercury.⁵ The data (viridicatin (1): CCDC 2524160) can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>.

- (1) STOE & Cie GmbH (2018) X-Area. software package for collecting single-crystal data on STOE area-detector diffractometers, for image processing, for the correction and scaling of reflection intensities and for outlier rejection. STOE & Cie GmbH, Darmstadt.
- (2) Sheldrick, G. Crystal structure refinement with SHELXL. *Acta Cryst. C* **2015**, *C71*, 3-8.
- (3) Sheldrick, G. A short history of SHELX. *Acta Cryst. A* **2008**, *A64*, 112-122.
- (4) FinalCif. <https://dkratzert.de/finalcif.html>.
- (5) Macrae, C. F.; Sovago, I.; Cottrell, S. J.; Galek, P. T. A.; McCabe, P.; Pidcock, E.; Platings, M.; Shields, G. P.; Stevens, J. S.; Towler, M.; Wood, P. A. Mercury 4.0: from visualization to analysis, design and prediction. *J. Appl. Cryst.* **2020**, *53*, 226-235.

2 Crystallographic Data:

Table S1. Crystal data and details of structure refinement for viridicatin.

Compound	Viridicatin (1)
CCDC number	2524160
Empirical formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂
Formula weight	237.25
Temperature [K]	210
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group (number)	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i> (14)
<i>a</i> [Å]	5.7785(5)
<i>b</i> [Å]	20.9663(18)
<i>c</i> [Å]	9.8243(8)
α [°]	90
β [°]	105.660(7)
γ [°]	90
Volume [Å ³]	1146.07(17)
<i>Z</i>	4
ρ_{calc} [gcm ⁻³]	1.375
μ [mm ⁻¹]	0.091
<i>F</i> (000)	496
Crystal size [mm ³]	0.300×0.500×0.800
Crystal colour	colorless
Crystal shape	long needle
Radiation	Mo <i>K</i> α (λ =0.71073 Å)
2 θ range [°]	5.80 to 66.07 (0.65 Å)
Index ranges	-6 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 8 -30 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 31 -14 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 14
Reflections collected	20388
Independent reflections	4059 <i>R</i> _{int} = 0.0209 <i>R</i> _{sigma} = 0.0142
Completeness to $\theta = 25.242^\circ$	99.8 %
Data / Restraints / Parameters	4059 / 0 / 166
Absorption correction <i>T</i> _{min} / <i>T</i> _{max} (method)	0.8671 / 0.9629 (sphere)
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.079
Final <i>R</i> indexes	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0464
[<i>I</i> ≥ 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	w <i>R</i> ₂ = 0.1370
Final <i>R</i> indexes	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0548
[all data]	w <i>R</i> ₂ = 0.1462
Largest peak/hole [eÅ ⁻³]	0.38/-0.20

3 Visualization of the crystal structure and molecular structure for viridicatin.

Figure S1: Molecular structure with crystallographic atom labeling of viridicatin. Atom labeling refers to the positional numbering used in the CIF file and differs from the numbering scheme used for NMR-data assignment. Displacement ellipsoids are shown at the 50% probability level.

Figure S2: ^1H - (red) and ^{13}C -NMR-Data (green), signal assignment and HMBC interactions (blue) for viridicatin.

Figure S3: ^1H NMR (500 MHz, acetone- d_6) of viridicatin. Full range.

F10 Acr 500.20.fid
F10 Acr * 1H * NEO500

Figure S4: ^1H NMR (500 MHz, acetone- d_6) of viridicatin. Range from 7.60 to 7.10 ppm

Figure S6: H,H-COSY (500 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) of viridicatin.

Figure S7: HSQC (500/125 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) of viridicatin.

Figure S8: HMBC (500/125 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) of viridicatin.

Figure S9: NOESY (500 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) of viridicatin.

